

Examining the Job Happiness Model in the Organizational Context: Evidence from Bahrain

Author's Details:

*⁽¹⁾Marwan Mohamed Abdeldayem ⁽²⁾Saeed Hameed AL Dulaimi-

⁽¹⁾⁽²⁾College of Administrative Sciences, Applied Science University (ASU), Kingdom of Bahrain. Email:

⁽³⁾Dheya Mohamed Alshaebani-Ministry of Industry, Commerce and Tourism, Kingdom of Bahrain

Abstract

Nowadays in most governmental and public organizations, motivating employees and enhancing their capabilities are the most complicated issues in Human Resources Management. It can be argued that organizational behavior is an exciting field of study which can help managers to handle human resources in an effective way in order to achieve the organizational goals. Previous studies in this field revealed that when employees are happy and satisfied at work, the productivity will increase and the management will be able to optimize available resources and improve the organizational performance. This study aims at examining the Job Happiness Model in the Organizational Context. Hence, employees' responses data has been collected using a questionnaire survey, in addition to some demographic variables that may be connected to job happiness such as gender, age, income, managerial level. The sample of the study includes 187 governmental employees from the Kingdom of Bahrain. A regression analysis was used to test the relationship between the independent variables (the four I's: I enjoy my work, I care about my health, I respect my colleagues and I love my family) and the dependent variable (job happiness). Although the results of the study reveal a significant and positive correlation between job happiness and the 4 I's, there is still a lot of things that the management in governmental organizations has to improve and work on in order to make their organizations more effective and efficient.

Keywords: Job Happiness, The Four I's Model (I love, I care, I enjoy and I respect), HR Wellbeing, Organizational Behavior, Governmental Organizations, HRM, Kingdom of Bahrain.

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the last two decades several studies attempted to make human beings happy in any setup or situation, and huge budgets have been spent to achieve this goal (Covey, 2004). It is obvious that employees are the most critical asset in any organization as, without them, organizations will not exist or continue (CIPD, 2017). The smart Human Resource is a tool to make the work distinct by making the person who runs this work distinct. It is the aim of any organization to give the work a new dose of excellence; hence, it becomes a source of experience, skills development and building relationships. Such a practice would benefit the work itself away from making the work a source of psychological pressures and frustrations.

The requirement of Smart HRM Professional in creating a better employer to employee relations that inspire employees to accomplish individual and organizational goals. Lack of such professionals brings restrained industrial relations which stimulates widespread turmoil, stressed employee the executives relations, absence of certainty. Exclusive requirements of employees, development of militancy in worker's organizations and so forth are the variables that have made a hole among laborers and administrations. Without coordination in an association the execution of specialists is antagonistically influenced.

Furthermore, there is a refinement of workplace in industrialized nations like Japan, USA, and Germany. Globalization of economy has presented government segment to universal challenge as well. Enhancement in productivity and nature of work can come just when laborers deliberately create hierarchical responsibility. HRM approach helps in making a feeling of pride for the organization among work compel.

Matching the ever-increasing demands with changing environment, the business environment is rapidly

changing. Technological improvements have revolutionized production procedures. Automation has been introduced in office operations for better communication. It has revolutionized vital areas of business. There is a need to change for good to match with new and changing situations. This has expanded pressure on employees. The mechanical changes have required the utilization of modern machines. The establishment checking of machines, support and controlling of tasks need prepared and apt individuals

There is a continuous necessity for value addition & knowledge sharing of people for coping with the new emerging challenges. Human resource development has become vital for each and every institution. Research and fresh initiatives in industry require new policy amendments of human resource development and overall change in the approach. All management and the owners of commercial and non-commercial organizations irrespective whether they deal with products or services provide a good and healthy organizational climate. Every organization has its own individual unique organizational climate. Some organizations offer existing organizations by providing satisfying, happier and cheerful assets. While some fail to provide a good organizational climate it's a moral, social obligation of management and owner to provide a better and psychological environment.

HRM is the “process of management that develops and manages the human elements of the enterprise. It is not only the management of skills but also the attitude and aspirations of people when individuals come to workplace; they come with not only technical skills, knowledge experience but also with their personal feelings, desires, motives, attitude value, etc.”, (Abdldayem & Aldulaimi, 2018). It involves the application of management functions and principles. The functions and principles are applied to acquisitions, developing, maintaining and enumerating employees in organization.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

The main purpose of this research is to motivate the work environment by making the employees happy and satisfied with what they are doing at work; the research also addresses following objectives:

- To identify the requirement of job happiness and the four I's.
- To analyze the level of satisfaction of employees at a governmental organization in the Kingdom of Bahrain.
- To model the relationship between the four I's and the job happiness of the sampled employees.
- To explore whether the four factors mentioned above are having a strong relationship with the Job happiness.

The most important values of this study for all employees in the working environment under Job Happiness are:

- Importance of being healthy.
- Importance of enjoying work.
- Respecting employee's colleagues.
- Importance of family.

This research will shed some light on the job happiness and its related aspects. It explains how to establish a motivated environment where the governmental employees can achieve the organizational goals in an efficient way and at the same time makes the work itself enjoyable. Also, how to make a good job environment and to manage emotions and flexibility in dealing with employees. Therefore, managers can make the work optimism the basis for developing the employees themselves. Furthermore, how to create a job environment that can assist employees in balancing their working life, family life, and establishing a healthy environment that will maintain the employee's health in terms of building the body, sound mind, control of concerns and overcome the pain. Figure (1) below shows the four I's that represent the main axes of the development initiative.

Figure (1) Main axes of the development initiative

The main axes of the initiative are the four I's:

- 1- I care about my health.
- 2- I enjoy my work.
- 3- I respect my colleagues.
- 4- I love my family.

The main idea of this research is to reveal how to establish a motivated environment where the governmental employees can achieve the organizational goal in an efficient way and at the same makes the work itself enjoyable in relation to the 4 I's. Organizational climate is a relatively enduring quality of the internal environment experience by the member influence the behavior and can be described in terms of value of the organization. It is important for any organization to obtain expert opinion on the climate and find out whether the employees are satisfied because it greatly influences the productivity and efficiency of organization. Therefore the below questions need to be answered?

1. What are the factors influencing job Happiness?
2. What is the most influencing factor of job happiness?
3. What are the factors that need to be provided in the organization that can increase their job happiness?

Based on the statement of the problem, the following research objectives were framed.

A hypothesis is framed to find meaningful findings for the stated objectives. Well identified hypotheses and theories are based on well-constructed research questions.

H0- All the variables (I love, I care, I enjoy and I respect) equally influence Job Happiness.

The outcome of the research will be essential to all readers who are really interested in being satisfied with their jobs.

- Analysis of the data collected from the questionnaire has been made on the assumption that the data provided by respondents are accurate.
- The study has been restricted to all the employees of the Government sector.
- Time constraint.

HRM helps in creating a better understanding between employees and management it helps employees in accomplishing individual and organizational goals, HRM approach helps in creating a sense of pride for the organization among the workforce. Job Happiness defined as a measure of the satisfaction of workers in their job whether they like the job or the individual aspects

What is the Wellbeing MOIC initiative?

Figure (2) below shows the Wellbeing MOIC. This initiative makes the work itself enjoyable and the ability to manage the emotions and flexibility in dealing with employees and optimism work as a basis for the development of the employees themselves, and makes employees able to balance their career and family life commitments, and the establishment of a healthy environment to maintain their health, which is reflected positively on the building of the body and the sound mind and control the concerns and overcome the pain.

Figure (2) The Wellbeing MOIC

It is a tool to make the work distinct by making the person who runs this work distinct. It is the rooting of the principle of "worship work" as stated in all heavenly messages, and that "work is a national duty" considering that this work strengthens the countries work environment. This is an opportunity to strengthen belonging and loyalty to the kingdom of Bahrain. And this initiative gives the work a new dose of excellence to be a source of experience and skills development and to build relationships that benefit the work itself away from making the work a source of psychological pressure and frustration and the source of bad relations with staff and that each achievement of the work is the happiness of others and contribute to building the future and the example of the noble values of the employee in the love of giving and helping others in the field of work and the establishment of the principle of tolerance, ethics and cultivate a culture of appreciation and respect.

Initiatives:

I enjoy my work: by creating a positive and positive work environment to keep up with the work of the employee and to unleash creativity in his work.

I care about my health: I am interested in the health culture and strengthening it by providing a healthy environment that helps the employee to perform his work with all activity.

I respect my colleagues: the consolidation of positive relationships between employees at the workplace.

I love my family: enhancing the employee's relationship with his family to achieve family happiness and social role in the development of society to reverse the happy relationship to work by creating the positive spirit of the employee.

According to Paige Williams, Margaret L. Kren and Lean Walters in their article titled 'Exploring Selective Exposure and Confirmation Bias as Processes Underlying Employee Work Happiness (2016) (see figure (3) below). They have highlighted a process of job happiness and how does it properly work. There are internal and external factors that have direct effect on the employee's behavior in the workforce at the organization. They have described that the internal factors are beliefs, behavior and value. The external factors are job characteristics, employee's colleagues, direct managers or officer and work atmosphere. For example, if the organization's management takes a proper strategy, then the work environment will be influenced. By having an appropriate strategy and healthy work environment, it will lead to job happiness and satisfaction for the employees themselves.

There are internal and external factors involved in human resources management. Internal Factors include the human resources management and human resources development are used interchangeably. In addition, information and growth plans of the organizations should be carefully analyzed to judge their impact on manpower requirements in future. Materials are also the most important things which are needed for the production of the sources the materials should be sent in right time and at the right place to the right person at the time of production which helps the organization to reach the goals of the company, within the specified time and reach the target of the organization. External Factors include the political environment, economic environment, social environment and technical environment (Abdeldayem & Aldulaimi, 2018).

The study of technological development is becoming essential for understanding the organizational behavior since people are influenced by the technological development. Organizational climate refers to the total environment in which people in the organization work. No organization can ignore organizational climate because it influences the behavior of the person. Therefore, many researchers agree that a sound organization climate is extremely important for the ultimate achievement of organizational goals. Organizational climate through a concise concept is normally associated with job performance, job satisfaction, and Job morale of employee.

Figure (3) Development framework (Paige Williams, Margaret L.Kren and Lean Walters 2016)

The above model in figure (3) describes the outside-in factors (organization level) such as positive climate, positive relationship, positive communication and positive meeting which will create positive culture by introducing forgiveness, trust, integrity optimism and compassion. The inside-out factors (Individual level) such as training, mentoring and job shadowing will create hope optimum, self-efficacy and resilience. Both internal and external factors will subsequently lead to employee work happiness, organization commitment, job satisfaction, and work engagement.

The current study has used the above stated theory and after analyzing the problem statement has framed the below conceptual framework as stated in table (1) below Table (1) displays the independent variables and dependent variable of the study. The independent variables are expected to affect the dependent variable. Cause-effect relationships frequently include several independent variables that affect the dependent variable. Therefore, the organization’s top management has to invest in the four I’s (I enjoy my work, I care about my health, I respect my colleagues, and I love my family) in order to achieve job happiness which will increase the efficiency and productivity.

Table (1) shows the relationship between the Independent and dependent variables. It is clearly indicated that the if the four I’s (I enjoy my work, I care about my health, I respect my colleagues and I love my family) are considered then it will lead to creating Job Happiness at work. The connection between dependent and independent variables is too common.

Table (1) a list of Independent and dependent variables

Dependent Variable	Independent Variables
Job Happiness	<p>I enjoy my work: by creating a positive work environment to keep up with the work of employees and to unleash creativity in their work.</p> <p>I care about my health: I am interested in the health culture and strengthening it by providing a healthy environment that helps employees to perform their work with all activities.</p> <p>I respect my colleagues: the consolidation of positive relationships between employees at the workplace.</p> <p>I love my family: enhancing the employee's relationship with their family to achieve family happiness and social role in the development of society to reverse the happy relationship to work by creating the positive spirit of employees.</p>

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section (2) presents the literature review. The methodology of the study is in section (3). Section (4) explains the analysis and empirical findings, and section (5) concludes and provides some recommendations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

A number of studies have been alone in the field of organizational climate ranging from the dimensions of climate to the influence of climate on the behavior of the employees. Lallan Prasad and Banerjee (2012) shed light on the importance of human resources management in modern corporate structure along with the responsibilities and roles of human resource employees. It highlighted the analysis of work environment in relation to management.

It was also found that high level of organizational commitment tend to be associated with low level of absenteeism and turnover more committed individuals are less likely to look for new jobs than less committed ones, and it was also found that organizational commitment is associated with high levels of willingness to share and make sacrifices nonwork lives. Employees are ready to exert extra effort for or on behalf of the organization when they have a strong faith in the values and beliefs of an organization and readily accept its goals and objectives. Commitment as the psychological attachment felt by the person for the organization (Aldulaimi, 2018). In addition, they are considered to have a decent level of organizational commitment. (Alsamman et al. 2016)

According to Greece (2015), the prosperity is not just about individuals' wellbeing, yet it's a mix between two factors the wellbeing and the prosperity. It feels very esteemed and upheld in the activity they do in their work environment. It's additionally about their execution, efficiency and wellbeing and which is normally leads to

great primary concern numbers for the association. Business associations that are all around organized and very much oversee, for the most part, assume a basic job in the advancement of workers' wellbeing and obviously the general prosperity. The advantages they acquire result the decrease of truancy and malingering and encourage simplicity and speed of recuperation and come back to work after either genuine damage or sickness. It's about most straightforward definition; prosperity is about close to home bliss, feeling better and carrying out one's responsibility in a safe and in sound condition.

Nowadays various people possibly ask themselves "How I can be happy in work environment?" This is an issue in light of the fact that multiple occasions people tend to disassociate happiness and joy with one's work. Anyway this idea "happiness" is not inverse with one's work. Several studies such as Saari and Judge (2004), and Rodriguez and Sanz (2011) have guaranteed that there might be a reliable connection between employment fulfillment and life fulfillment. For that nearby interrelation, Asiyabi and Mirabi (2012), recommend that happy and cheerful representatives can convey their satisfaction from their office to home to and furthermore exchange their bliss from their home to office (Wesarat, Yazam, and Halim, 2014). At the end of the day, work adds to prosperity and satisfaction in various ways (Warr, 2007; Fisher, 2010). For example, joblessness diminishes singular prosperity, and they recouped again when they get a new line of work (Clark et al. 2008). Then, bliss at work spot relies upon individual work and life fulfillment (Bhattacharjee and Bhattacharjee, 2010).

Furthermore, in the globalization time, companies and business organizations need to confront nonstop changes as high challenge since today has significantly expanded internationalization, speed, new innovation and furthermore new authoritative practices since requirements and estimations of workers and clients are evolving (Wesarat, Yazam, and Halim, 2014). Along these lines, firms need to adjust to intensity conditions and be proficient to endure and to have achievement, particularly in a troublesome commercial center as the ongoing worldwide money related emergency. Today, in this circumstance is basic the job of representatives since they have to adjust fast to changes, ready to work with others, should be energetic and talented, have a decent frame of mind and be in charge of the association, for that reason is essential to work with cheerful and happy (Januwarsono, 2015). Various early specialists of the executives (for example Snow, 1923; Mayo, 1924; Putnam, 1930; Kornhauser, 1933) thought consummately that "human" assets were a reasonable, supportable wellspring of upper hand. These early scientists obviously comprehended the critical job of specialist bliss played on individual proficiency and hierarchical wellbeing (Luthans, Luthans and Luthans, 2004).

Subsequently, despondency or unhappiness at the working environment may diminish efficiency of the company and furthermore increment a more elevated amount of truancy at work spot (Fereidouni, Najdi, and Amiri, 2013). Also, agreeing Pryce-Jones (2010), gauges that a representative works a normal of 90,000 hours along his life. This gigantic number of hours ought to stir the feeling of criticalness to look for joy and happiness at work and occupation fulfillment (Rodríguez and Sanz, 2011).

To conclude, various studies have revealed that cheerful and happy workers will, in general, be progressively beneficial and furthermore increasingly imaginative and creative, on the grounds that they produce new thoughts and attempt to do a similar activity in various approaches to spare time and enhance adequacy (Gupta, 2012). In addition, happy workers are more beneficial than the individuals who are miserable in light of the fact that they may not give careful consideration to undertakings (Wesarat, Yazam, and Halim, 2014). In this manner, happiness of workers not just methods for the organization representatives with higher efficiency, likewise assumes representatives who care about the quality, absence of stress and fatigue, more elevated amount of offers since representatives serve much better clients, additionally they are increasingly open to change and a higher stock execution (Alipour, 2012; Januwarsono, 2015). Pryce-Jones (2010) likewise bolsters this and has appeared in his profundity investigate the tremendous effect of the upbeat representatives (Alipour, 2012; Januwarsono 2015)

In the present financial atmosphere where we have to expand our finance ventures, the general absence of refinement of remuneration the board rehearses in numerous associations is astonishing and should be a key territory of center and improvement inside the human capital administration field.

3. METHODOLOGY

This section presents the methodology of the study. It explains the data collection process using a questionnaire survey and the statistical techniques employed to analyze the data. The questionnaire survey has been directed to a sample of 187 governmental employees from the Kingdom of Bahrain. Since the primary hypothesis of this research is to ascertain if there is a relationship between job happiness and employee productivity, the survey includes several questions such as:

- What is your gender?
- What is your age group?
- What is your management level at work?
- What is your monthly income?
- How long have you been working in this organization?
- How happy are you at work?
- I would refer others to work here.
- I have a clear understanding of my career/promotion path.
- On a scale of 1 to 10, how would you rate the balance between your work and personal life? (10 is most balanced)

The questionnaire is designed based on a 5 point Likert scale: Strongly Agree, Agree, Neither Agree nor Disagree, Disagree and Strongly Agreed in order to allow the audience to express their level of acceptance through the survey.

The tool of analysis: Data collected from various sources are carefully computed, classified, tabulated, analyzed and interpreted. The methods used for analyzing the data collected from the various sources are tabulated with the help of Tables, Charts, and Graphs to analyze the data. Regression analysis was used to test the relationship between the independent and dependent variables.

4. ANALYSIS AND EMPIRICAL FINDINGS

Researchers often find data analysis as the most enjoyable part of carrying out a research study, since, after all the hard work and writing, they get a chance to find out the answers. So, analyzing the data and interpreting the results are the reward for the work of collecting the data. Data analysis is a body of methods that helps to term facts, detect patterns, and develop all of the sciences. It can be used in different types of business, an organization's administration, and multiple policies. It discloses what the researcher can identify. This section includes the analysis and interpretation of data based on the survey conducted among the government employees in the surveyed area.

The government-industry has been developed during the past years in relation to the on-going changes and challenges in the overall economic environment. Actually, people have a wrong idea about the employees who work in the government sector that they are less effective and less productive compared to those who work in the private sector. Nowadays, the work environment has been changed dramatically and most of the public sector employees are qualified and well skilled. It is really important for the ministries management to understand the requirements and the issues of their employees in order to motivate the workforce and increase their productivity. This will be determined if they focus on the model of the four I's.

First, the profile of the respondents has been analysed. Then, the perception of the respondents to the four I's has been analysed and the relationship between demographic variables and the knowledge has been examined.

GENDER-WISE DISTRIBUTION OF THE RESPONDENTS

Gender is an important variable socio-demographic factor in any economic study. The gender-wise distribution of the respondents supports understanding the income-generating potential, the power of decision-making in family and the knowledge about the environment in which they live. Table (2) and figure (4) below display gender-wise distribution of the respondents

Table (2):gender-wise distribution of the respondents

		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	78	41.7
	Female	109	58.3
	Total	187	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Figure (4) the gender distribution of the respondents

The gender-wise distribution shows that the composition of the male is 41.7% and female is 58.3%. It also shows that 78 respondents are from male category and 109 respondents are from female category.

AGE-WISE DISTRIBUTION OF THE RESPONDENTS

Further, age is a notable factor in making considerable changes in the income earning capacity and decision making in any family. Table (3) and figure (5) show the age group of the entrepreneurs, which helps us to identify the most dominant age category which is involved in the job happiness in the government sector.

TABLE (3) AGE OF THE RESPONDENTS

		Frequency	Percentage
Age Group	18-25	14	7.5
	26-40	116	62.0
	41-55	54	28.9
	56-65	3	1.6
	Total	187	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Figure (5) AGE OF THE RESPONDENTS

Table (4) indicates that, out of 187 respondents, 116 (62%) of the respondents fall in the age group of 26-40 years, 54 (28.9%) are in the age group 41-55 years, 14 (7.5%) are in the age group of 18-25. There are only 3 (1.6%) are at the age of 56 -65 years.

MANAGEMENT LEVEL OF THE RESPONDENTS

Moreover, the management level plays an important role in identifying the related factors in job happiness. The management level respondents are described in the table (4) below.

TABLE (4) MANAGEMENT LEVEL

		Frequency	Percentage
Management Level	Operational Management	86	46.0
	Tactical/Middle Management	72	38.5
	Strategic Management	29	15.5
	Total	187	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Table (4) indicates that 46% of the respondents are from the operational management level, the next highest respondent’s percentage is from Tactical/Middle Management that is 38.5% while the last percentage is from the Strategic Management that is 15.5%.

MONTHLY INCOME OF THE RESPONDENTS

In addition, the monthly income or financial level of the employees is described as one of the major factors in making them happy and satisfied at work. The table below shows the respondents from employees based on their income

TABLE (5) Monthly Income

		Frequency	Percentage
Monthly Income	Less than 1000 BD	81	43.3
	1001 - 2000	80	42.8
	More Than 2000	26	13.9
	Total	187	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Table (5) reveals that the highest respondents are from employees who earn less than BHD 1,000 (43.3%) which is too close with the employees' salaries of the range of BHD 1,001 ~ 2,000 percentage (42.8%). The lowest percentage of 13.9 is from employees who earn more than BHD 2,000.

CURRENT WORK EXPERIENCE

Furthermore, table (6) shows the current work experience in the years of the 187 employees.

TABLE (6) Work Experience in years

		Frequency	Percent
Current Work Experience	Less Than One Year	5	2.7
	1 Year - 3 Years	28	15.0
	3 Years - 5 Years	25	13.4
	5 Years - 10 Years	36	19.3
	More than 10 Years	93	49.7
	Total	187	100.0

Source: Primary Data

It can be seen from the table (6) that the maximum percentage of the respondents is 49.7% for employees who worked more than 10 years while the minimum percentage is 2.7% for employees who worked less than one year.

LEVEL OF HAPPINESS AT WORK

Table (7) below shows the level of Happiness at Work categorise in five different mechanisms which have examined the 187 employees.

TABLE (7) HAPPINESS AT WORK

		Frequency	Percentage
Happiness at Work	Very Unhappy	7	3.7
	Unhappy	21	11.2
	Neutral	51	27.3
	Happy	89	47.6
	Very Happy	19	10.2
	Total	187	100.0

Source: Primary Data

It can be observed that the maximum percentage of the respondents is 47.6% for employees who are actually happy at work while the minimum percentage is 3.7% for employees who are very unhappy at work.

IDENTIFYING THE MOST INFLUENCING OF THE 4 I'S

The identified four factors have resulted in six regression factor scores. The six calculated regression factor score is used in the multiple regression analyses to investigate the capability of the factors in highlighting the

most important factors. The factor scores are used as independent variables and job happiness as a dependent variable. The regression factor scores predict the location or distance of each individual variable on the factor or component. A value is nearer to 0 means that the variable is near the average of the factor in which it is included. Tables (8), (9), (10) and (11) below show the findings related to the respondents' opinion in the four I's: IR, IE, IL and IC respectively.

Table (8) findings related to I respect my colleagues (IR).

	Strongly Disagree (%)	Disagree (%)	Neutral (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly Agree (%)
I would refer others to work here [IR]	4 (2.1%)	29 (15.5%)	52 (27.8%)	74 (39.6%)	28 (15.0%)
I frequently receive recognition from my manager [IR]	11 (5.9%)	19 (10.2%)	56 (29.9%)	71 (38.0%)	30 (16.0%)
I am very comfortable giving upwards feedback to my supervisor [IR]	8 (4.3%)	25 (13.4%)	33 (17.6%)	76 (40.6%)	45 (24.1%)
There is respect between team members in our organization [IR]	7 (3.7%)	15 (8.0%)	33 (17.6%)	78 (41.7%)	54 (28.9%)

Table (9) findings related to I enjoy my work (IE).

	Strongly Disagree (%)	Disagree (%)	Neutral (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly Agree (%)
I have a clear understanding of my career/promotion path [IE]	16 (8.6%)	25 (13.4%)	30 (16.0%)	85 (45.5%)	31 (16.6%)
I feel valued at work [IE]	13 (7.0%)	12 (6.4%)	42 (22.5%)	86 (46.0%)	34 (18.2%)
I have fun at work [IE]	16 (8.6%)	23 (12.3%)	50 (26.7%)	72 (38.5%)	26 (13.9%)
I foresee myself working here 3 to 5 years from now [IE]	9 (4.8%)	15 (8.0%)	58 (31.0%)	77 (41.2%)	28 (15.0%)

Table (10) findings related to I love my family (IL).

	Strongly Disagree (%)	Disagree (%)	Neutral (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly Agree (%)
I believe I am able to reach my full potential here [IL]	12 (6.4%)	29 (15.5%)	50 (26.7%)	61 (32.6%)	35 (18.7%)
I Believe my line manager is concerned about my family [IL]	10 (5.3%)	18 (9.6%)	57 (30.5%)	67 (35.8%)	35 (18.7%)
I believe our executive team contribute to a positive work culture here [IL]	14 (7.5%)	26 (13.9%)	47 (25.1%)	65 (34.8%)	35 (18.7%)
I like to see my work fellows and discuss with them on different issues [IL]	3 (1.6%)	11 (5.9%)	41 (21.9%)	85 (45.5%)	47 (25.1%)

Table (11) findings related to I care about my health (IC).

	Strongly Disagree (%)	Disagree (%)	Neutral (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly Agree (%)
I balance my work and personal life [IC]	5 (2.7%)	22 (11.8)	50 (26.7%)	75 (40.1%)	35 (18.7)
I believe the leadership team takes my feedback seriously [IC]	11 (5.9%)	29 (15.5%)	46 (24.6%)	69 (36.9%)	32 (17.1%)
I feel like the management team here is transparent [IC]	24 (12.8%)	31 (16.6%)	57 (30.5%)	53 (28.3%)	22 (11.8%)
I feel happy when I come to work in the morning [IC]	18 (9.6%)	18 (9.6%)	65 (34.8%)	58 (31.0%)	28 (15.0%)

A regression analysis of the identified factors and job happiness indicates the variations in preference caused by the four factors. Consequently, it supports the ministries and to concentrate their efforts and policies in those factors which have the strongest influence on the job happiness by the people in the surveyed area. The job happiness is taken as the dependent variable and the identified four factors are taken as the independent variables. The independent variables are I Respect (IR), I Enjoy (IE), I Love (IL) and I Care (IC).

H0: All the variables IR, IE, IL and IC equally influence the job happiness.

Table (12) below summarizes the regression model summary.

Table (12) Regression Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.653 ^a	.426	.413		.730

a. Predictors: (Constant), I Care, I Enjoy, I Respect, I Love

The regression model summary, which includes R, R², adjusted R², and the standard error, is presented in the table (12) The R-value (correlation coefficient) is estimated to be as 0.653, which indicates high positive correlation among the dependent and independent variables. The R² value for the estimated equation is 0.426, which is significant at 1 % level of probability. It shows that 42.6% of the variations in job happiness at work are explained by the four factors.

Table (13) ANOVA Analysis

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	71.844	4	17.961	33.737	.000 ^b
	Residual	96.894	182	.532		
	Total	168.738	186			

a. Dependent Variable: Happiness at Work

b. Predictors: (Constant), I Care, I Enjoy, I Respect, I Love

The results of ANOVA are presented in the table (13). The ‘F’ statistic value is 33.737, which is significant at 1% level of probability. It indicates that the independent variables influence significantly the variation in employee’s preference in job happiness. Also, the significance of R² as tested by the F statistic indicates that

the regression equation stated below is significant. Table (14) shows the regression coefficients. The estimated regression model for Job Happiness is:

$$JH = IR + IE + IL + IC$$

$$JH = .269 IR + .336 IE + .095 IL + .114 IC$$

Table (14) Regression Coefficients of Dependent Variable: Happiness at Work

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.511	.264		1.936	.054
	I Respect	.269	.099	.241	2.703	.008
	I Enjoy	.336	.097	.295	3.480	.001
	I Love	.095	.098	.087	.968	.334
	I Care	.114	.074	.124	1.542	.125

The regression results are shown in table (14) indicate that all the independent variables positively influence the Job Happiness. This is justifiable because when these employees getting excellent level of respect, enjoying their work, caring about each other and loving their family at the same time then it will be definitely resulting in overall job happiness at work. Moreover the IR, IE, IL, and IC factors are statistically significant. Thus the null hypothesis (H) is rejected as the results show that all the independent variables do not equally influence the cause for Job Happiness.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The resulting conclusion of this research is drawn based on the existing data analysis gathered from different employee’s levels from different departments in the government. 187 surveys have been conducted.

It is believed that a vast majority of employees felt that they are fully satisfied with the salary comparing to the current duties as per their existing job description. Organization’s top Management has to invest in the four I’s (I enjoy my work, I care about my health, I respect my colleagues, and I love my family) in order to achieve job happiness which will increase the efficiency and productivity in the organization.

With regard to the recent surveys conducted on the research, it shows the following findings:

- 47.1% of the survey shows that employees agree with the (I Respect) factor.
- 50.8% of the survey shows that employees agree with the (I Enjoy) factor.
- 41.2% of the survey shows that employees agree with the (I Love) factor.
- 39.6% of the survey shows that employees agree with the (I Care) factor.

By looking at the above findings, top management in governmental organizations should be aware of the associated factors that are influencing to create job happiness at work. They have clearly shown that not all employees have the same opinion. Some believe that enjoying work is the main opinion and others believe respecting their colleagues is the most important factor.

Job happiness depends on different types of factors as stated, many of that are within employee's control. The results of this research effort are in line with the findings of some previous studies, such as the study of Abdulwahab S. Bin Shmailan (2016), who had explained that the successful organizations should study and identify employee's satisfaction, performance and employee's engagements which are crucial. The execution destinations are one of the capacity and targets that required being in the association as these goals will assist the association with initiating new development for the beginning and with gauging such execution of the workers. Just as to ensure that the representatives know about the goal and system of the entire association through their execution survey to be in accordance with the association mission and vision.

Furthermore, it is extremely important to know how employees feel about their employer and organization whether it is positive or negative feelings. This can determine the level of performance and needs to be treated individually (Jane Bucher, 2004). How satisfied employees are with their job depends on their values and motives. It is concluded that all the variables IR, IE, IL, and IC equally influence the job happiness.

Although the results of the study show a significant and positive correlation between job happiness and the 4 I's (I enjoy my work, I care about my health, I respect my colleagues, and I love my family), there is still a lot of things that the ministries' management has to work on and improve in order to make their organizations more effective and efficient. The results show that less than half of the employees feel that they care about their health. Since, as the common adage says "health is wealth," management must take further steps to improve the awareness of employees in the benefits of taking care of one's health. This can be done with health seminars and inviting health experts to talk about the long-term benefits of taking care of one's mind and body. Perhaps, free gym memberships or health and nutrition clinic promos can be arranged for selected employees.

In addition, less than half of the respondents feel that they respect their colleagues. This is a bit alarming considering that a healthy work environment necessitates a good working relationship among colleagues with mutual understanding and respect shared among them, regardless of personal background. Management can facilitate leadership seminars and team-building workshops to promote a healthy working relationship among colleagues in the same workplace.

Also, less than half of the respondents feel that they love their families. This is also alarming since it might be an indication that more employees love their careers more than their jobs. Management can mitigate this by inviting workers in family gatherings such as picnics during the weekends or sponsored family vacations to employees who deserve such rewards.

More than 50% of respondents feel that they enjoy their jobs and this is only normal because for some employees, their job is their only means of livelihood and they have no option but to learn to enjoy it, despite the daily challenges they face while working. However, to increase this percentage, management has to consider career-enhancing systems like the promotion and career advancement systems; performance appraisal and rewards system; and other systems that enhance positive worker attitude and job happiness. Another recommendation is that further studies should be conducted on how to improve the implementation of the job happiness activities by identifying specific activities that significantly contribute to the overall job happiness.

REFERENCES

- i. *Abdeldayem Marwan M and Saeed Hameed Aldulaimi (2018), The Economic Islamicity Index, between Islamicity and Universality: Critical Review and Discussion. International Business Management, Vol. (12), 46-52.*
- ii. *Abdulwahab S. Bin Shmailan (2016). The relationship between job satisfactions, job performance and employee engagement.*

- iii. Aldulaimi, Saeed Hameed (2018), *Examining the relationship between transformational leadership model and organizational commitment model to enhance decision making participation: evidence from the kingdom of Bahrain*. *Global journal of engineering science and researches*. 5 (1), 23-28
- iv. Alipour, Ali, H. Safarzaddeh, A. Soloukdar, and A. Parpanchi. (2012), "The Role of Emotionality and Power on Tendency to Unethical Behaviors", *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 4(2), 187-196.
- v. Asiyabi, M., and Mirabi, V. (2012). *Investigation of contributing factors in employees' desertion in power engineering consultants (Moshanir) company*. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 4(6), 1183-1199.
- vi. Bhattacharjee, D., and Bhattacharjee, M. (2010). *Measuring happiness at work place*. *ASBM Journal of Management*, 3(1/2), 112-125
- vii. CIPD Factsheet. (2017). *Workforce Planning*. [ONLINE] Available at: <https://www.cipd.co.uk/knowledge/strategy/organisationaldevelopment/workforce-planning-factsheet#8035>. [Accessed 24 December 2017
- viii. Clark, A.E., Diener, E., Georgellis, Y., and Lucas, R. E. (2008). *Lags and Leads in Life Satisfaction: a Test of the Baseline Hypothesis*. *The Economic Journal*, 118, F222-F243.
- ix. Covey Stephen R (2004). *The seven habits of highly effective*. 8th Ed. New York: Free Press.
- x. Fisher, C.D. (2010). 'Happiness at work.' *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 12, 348-412.
- xi. Fereidouni, H.G., Najdi, Y., and Amiri, R.E. (2013). *Do governance factors matter for happiness in the MENA region?* *International Journal of Social Economics*, 40(12), 1028-1040.
- xii. Greene, R.J. (2015) *Aligning human capital strategy with organizational strategy*. *WorldatWork Journal*. Vol 24, No 2, second quarter. pp. 6-11.
- xiii. Gupta, V. (2012) 'Importance of being happy at work.' Institute for Research and Development India. Download from: http://www.irdindia.in/journal_ijrdmr/pdf/vol1_iss1/2.pdf [23 April 2016]
- xiv. Jane Boucher (2004). *How to Love the Job You Hate Job Satisfaction for the 21st Century*.
- xv. Januwarsono, S. (2015) 'Analytical of factors determinants of happiness at work case study on PT. PLN (persero) region Suluttengo, Sulawesi, Indonesia. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 7(8), 2015.
- xvi. Kornhauser, A. (1933). *The technique for measuring employee attitudes*. *Personnel Journal*, 9, 99-107.
- xvii. Lallan Prasad and A.M. Banerjee (2012). *Managing Human Resource Management*
- xviii. Luthans, F. Luthans, K.W. and Luthans B.C. (2004). *Psychological capital management: going beyond human and social capital*. *Business Horizons*, 47, 45-50.
- xix. Mayo, E. (1924). *Revery and industrial fatigue*. *Journal of Personnel Research*, 3, 273-281.
- xx. Paige Williams, Margaret L. Kren and Lean Walters (2016), *Exploring Selective Exposure and Confirmation Bias as Processes Underlying Employee Work Happiness*
- xxi. Pryce-Jones J. (2010). *Happiness at Work: Maximizing your Psychological Capital for Success*. Oxford, UK: Wiley.
- xxii. Putman, M.L. (1930). *Improving employee relations: A plan which uses data obtained from employees*. *Personnel Journal*, 8, 314-325.
- xxiii. Rodríguez, M.A. and Sanz V.I. (2011) 'La felicidad en el trabajo'. *Mente y cerebro*, No. 50/2011.
- xxiv. Saari, L.M., and Judge, T.A. (2004). *Employee attitudes and job satisfaction*. *Human Resource Management*, 43(4), 395-407.
- xxv. Snow, A.J. (1923). *Labour Turnover and Mental Alertness Test Scores*. *Journal of Applied Psychology* 7(3), 285-290
- xxvi. Warr, P. (2007). *Work, Happiness, and Unhappiness*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.
- xxvii. Wesarat, P., Yazam, M.S. and Halim, A.M.A. (2014) 'A conceptual framework of happiness at the workplace'. *Asian Social Science*, 11(2) at